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Research Article

**A STUDY TO ASSESS THE HARMFULNESS OF
BENZODIAZEPINE USE AMONG MEDICAL STUDENTS WITH
RESPECT TO GENDER, AGE, LOCALITY & MONTHLY
INCOME****¹Muhammad Kashif Shabbir, ²Kiran Fatima, ³Sarah Anwar**¹Latin American School of Medicine Havana Cuba²CMH Lahore Medical and Dental College³Akhtar Saeed Medical and Dental College, Lahore**Abstract:**

Objective: The research purpose is to determine how much harmful use of benzodiazepine prevails among the medical students.

Materials & Methods: We took 250 students, both gender medical students and studied them at Services Hospital, Lahore from January to September 2017. The students were in the age bracket of (18 – 25) years. Our excluding criteria were students having a history of chronic physical illness, and disorder of psychotic, mood, personality, and anxiety. We took informed consent from each student. Every student used and filled predesigned Pro-forma, which a single psychiatrist assessed for harmful use of benzodiazepine.

Results: Among 250 students, 76.8% (192) were more than 21 years. Male and female students were 75.6% (189) and 24.4% (61) respectively (3.1:1 of the male-to-female ratio) with (22.5 ± 2.1) years of mean age. Only 7.6% (19) students used benzodiazepine harmful.

Conclusion: We concluded that 7.6% harmful usage exists among medical students, which is a little higher percentage.

Keywords: Addiction, Medical Students (MS), Benzodiazepine (BZO) and Substance.

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INTRODUCTION:

BZOs widely prescription includes alprazolam, clonazepam, diazepam and lorazepam (Xanax, Valium, Klonopin, and Ativan respectively) and has its name among the top-100 most commonly prescribed medications [1]. BZO has an immediate effect generally and doctors prescribe it for short-term needs. Due to increase and decrease in anxiety disorders from time to time, patients prefer using BZO because of its judicious use [2]. There are plenty of reasons like presurgical sedation, muscle spasticity, convulsive/involuntary movement disorders, alcohol detoxification, and cardiovascular/gastrointestinal related anxiety conditions for which doctors prescribe BZO [3]. APA report shows an (11% - 15%) of adults having used BZOs one in the preceding year while (1% - 2%) have used it daily for a year or more [2]. The use, dependence, and abuse of BZO in general population are less than in the substance-abuse population in psychiatric-treatment settings [4, 5]. As BZO has abuse potential with controlled substances, doctors should prescribe it after consulting patients' addiction history. If a clinician understands the side-effects and toxicity of BZO, he may prescribe it with hypnotic and anxiolytic agents to reduce risks of medico-legal liability and improve treatment outcomes. As BZO has a rapid onset of action, addicts prefer it highly [6]. Chemical dependent patients highly reinforce such mood-changing medicines which are highly volatile (Vaporizable), potent, and soluble while using intravenously [7]. According to data, highly-lipophilic BZOs which rapidly cross the blood-brain barrier (Like diazepam, alprazolam/lorazepam, which has high potency) shows the highest reinforcement that's why to have a great chance of abuse [6]. Due to ease-of-access to drugs, work-stress, close contacts with death and illness, and sleep deprivation, health professionals and MSs show a high risk of harmful use of this substance. A study of MS shows a higher 17% of illicit medicine harmful use which is unacceptable and threatening to their patient-care abilities [8]. Physicians training at medical college goes through a significant physiological distress which may produce an unintended mental and emotional negativity/instability [9]. As MS hold special place and responsibilities, that is why society expects highly professionalism out of them [10]. Therefore, the use of substance poses risks of losing effectiveness and practical-fitness as future doctors among MS. According to a belief, physicians start using substance early and it is very important to study the lifestyles of MS to study substance-abuse [10 - 15]. Both genders uses BZO (especially during the exam) and is the only harmful substance [16]. Another study shows a 6.0% prevalence of BZO

harmful use among MS [9]. Globally, especially in Pakistan, BZO is notorious for its significant dependency and self-harm through the higher frequency of use [18]. Reasons like peer pressure, experimentation curiosity, academic stress, insomnia, and getting "high" lead 96%, 88%, 90%, 34%, and 88% students respectively towards using these drugs [19]. A study of Nepal shows hostel life, high expectations of parents, and huge syllabus whereas a study in Pakistan shows family depression history (28.90%) to be the main reasons stress [9]. The research purpose was to determine the prevailing harmful use of BZO among MS due to its wide acceptance of being a benign-sleeping-pills as no such study exists in past. This will prevail awareness among policymakers to discourage such harmful activities among MS to prevent future troubles.

Operational Definitions:

1. Medical student: First to Final Professional MBBS students (undergraduate)
2. Benzodiazepines: A tranquillizing drug of sedative and hypnotic action to control anxiety.
3. Harmful use: Use of BZO without physician's prescription within the last month (Once or more).

MATERIAL AND METHODS:

We took 250 students, both gender medical students and studied them at Services Hospital, Lahore from January to September 2017. The students were in the age bracket of (18 - 25) years. Our excluding criteria were students having a history of chronic physical illness, and disorder of psychotic, mood, personality, anxiety and students unwilling to participate.

After the recommendation of Ethical Review Committee, we took informed consent from 250 MS. Every student used and filled predesigned proforma, which a single psychiatrist assessed for harmful use of benzodiazepine. The two-part proforma consisted of demographic variables (Gender, age, and MBBS class) and study variables (Family Income/month, Home/Hostel residence, urban/rural background, and BZO intake frequency).

We used SPSS to analysed collected data. We used frequency and percentage to present qualitative data (Gender, BZO harmful use) however Mean \pm SD to present quantitative data (age). We controlled effect modifiers (age, locality, gender, monthly income) through stratification. We used graphs and tables to present results and Chi-Square test to present groups statistical difference. P-value of ≤ 0.05 was significant.

RESULTS:

Among 250 students of (18 – 25) years, 76.8% (192) were more than 21 years. Male and female students were 75.6% (189) and 24.4% (61) respectively (3.1:1 of the male-to-female ratio) with (22.5 ± 2.1) years of

mean age. Only 7.6% (19) students used benzodiazepine harmful. After stratification, the study did not find any significant difference in harmful use of BZO between age/gender groups.

Table – I: Age, Gender, Monthly Income, Locality and Benzodiazepine Harmful Use Stratification

Variables		Number	Percentage
Age	18 – 20 Years	58	23.2
	20 – 23 Years	94	37.6
	> 23 – 25 Years	98	39.2
Gender	Male	61	24.4
	Female	189	75.6
Monthly Income	1000 - 3000	51	20.4
	3000 - 5000	57	22.8
	5000 - 10,000	68	27.2
	Above 10,000	74	29.6
Residence	Urban	153	61.2
	Rural	97	38.8
Benzodiazepine Harmful Use	Yes	19	7.6
	No	231	92.4

Table – II: Benzodiazepine Harmful Use Stratification among Different Variables

Stratification		Yes		No		P-Value
		Number	Percentage	Number	Percentage	
Age	18 – 20 Years	1	1.72	57	98.28	0.142
	> 20 – 23 Years	8	8.51	86	91.49	
	> 23 – 25 Years	10	10.2	88	89.8	
Gender	Male	16	8.47	173	91.53	0.363
	Female	3	4.92	58	95.08	
Monthly Income	1000 - 3000	2	3.92	49	96.08	0.110
	> 3000 - 5000	2	3.51	55	96.49	
	> 5000 - 10000	5	7.35	92.65	92.65	
	> 10000	10	13.51	86.49	86.49	
Residence	Rural	5	5.15	94.85	94.85	0.268
	Urban	14	8.92	143	91.08	

DISCUSSION:

BZOs (also Benzos) are drugs used as minor tranquilizers. Doctors prescribe them to resolve sleep deprivation and anxiety. BZOs have thirty different types, each generic name sells under several names/brands of different companies [19]. BZO reduces central nervous system and brain's working

speed. BZOs help in sleeping and reducing anxiety medically to put the body into rest. To avoid its dependency, doctors prescribe them for short time (4 weeks maximum) [19, 20]. Its non-prescribed use is becoming a global concern. Due to lack of data, ineffective monitoring (of health-care professionals), and non-medical use, the actual scale of this issue is

unknown. Monitoring instruments and studies related to substance abuse cover alcohol, drugs (illegal), and tobacco. However, the most attention requiring thing is the use of prescribed drugs as non-medical in numerous ways [21, 22]. Medical associations and institutions, and researchers have raised concerns about psychoactive drug's non-medical use by physicians and MS [23, 24]. As physician themselves, sometimes, are involved in substance misuse but on the other hand, they can detect substance misuse at an early stage among their patients and colleagues providing appropriate services [23, 24]. The research purpose of our study is to determine how much harmful use of BZO prevails. We found 7.60% (19) students with BZO harmful use. A study shows this prevalence to be 6% [9]. Another research shows that the majority of MS are willing to self-prescribe BZO for short duration [17]. Ireland and UK studies shows (14%-35.60%) and 90% of illicit substance use and alcohol use respectively which is way higher than our research's and subcontinent's studies' findings [24 – 26]. The study of Magalhaes et al. did in 1991 shows 5% BZO harmful use among 1069 students of the university [27]. Mesquita et al. show in his study (1995) 11% of prevalence in the same institute [11]. Harmful use of BZO among female students was more protective even after taking non-prescribed drugs, alcohol, tobacco, age and year of study into adjustments [25]. However, Western studies find this gender-gap to be small and found a higher rate of women with harmful substance use [15]. Women with excessive use of alcohol also show clear evidence of psychological, physiological, and medical harm [28]. Various studies describe this arising problem among medical/correlated students. Doctors with substance use show not only personal health risks but also professional inefficiencies improper patients' check-up, negligent behaviour, and personal health problems. Physicians using addictive substances may receive patients with the same issue less seriously [25]. Reasons for the substance use among college students are many like reduction of social, academic stress, social needs, recreation, the pursuit of pleasure, curiosity, making friends, improving energy levels to increase study times/academic performance and increase concentration [29, 30]. Moreover, MS have easy access to psychiatric drugs [29]. Moore et al. in his studies identify precursors of drug abuse of medical school including excessive smoking and alcohol intake, less religious affiliation, alcohol intake in public, anger in response to stress and anxiety. The risks-factors for substance use include higher academic-ranking, idealism/perfectionism in behaviour, and success in predicting traits [32, 33]. Lastly, we conclude that BZO harmful use, which

7.6% among MS, is a little bit higher.

CONCLUSION:

We concluded that 7.6% harmful usage exists among MS, which a little high percentage. So, we recommend awareness campaigns to discourage this practice among MS.

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